

Dr. Eliot's Diagnosis of Hamlet's 'Malady'

Vikas Rana

Assistant Professor in English

T.J.C.M Govt.Degree College, Sujampur Tihra, Distt. Hamirpur (H.P)

Received : 18/05/2024

1st BPR : 24/05/2024

2nd BPR : 30/05/2024

Accepted : 06/06/2024

Abstract

T.S. Eliot's essay, "Hamlet and His Problems," offers a groundbreaking interpretation of Shakespeare's *Hamlet*, challenging traditional views of the character's madness. Eliot, a modernist poet and critic, suggests that Hamlet's struggle is not merely personal but universal, reflecting the complexities and contradictions inherent in the human condition. His analysis diverges from earlier Romantic and psychological criticisms, arguing that the play's true issue is Shakespeare's failure to provide a suitable "objective correlative" for Hamlet's intense emotions. Eliot posits that the play's lack of a coherent emotional anchor contributes to its artistic shortcomings, marking it as an "artistic failure." This perspective shifts the focus from Hamlet's actions to his existential dilemmas, highlighting the play's exploration of existential themes and moral ambiguities. Eliot's insights have significantly influenced modern literary criticism, providing a framework for understanding Hamlet's psychological depth and its reflection on human nature.

Key words: Dr. Eliot, Hamlet, Malady.

William Shakespeare's *Hamlet* has intrigued audiences and scholars alike for centuries. Among the myriad interpretations of Hamlet's character, one of the most profound analyses comes from T.S. Eliot. T. S. Eliot's essay on "Hamlet and His Problems" (Sacred Wood, 95-103) is, to put it crudely, the ultimate step in dis-integrationist thinking about one of Shakespeare's greatest tragedies. The essay is in fact Eliot's review of two books that appeared in 1919: E. E. Stoll's *Hamlet: An Historical and Comparative Study* and J. M. Robertson's *Problem of "Hamlet."* T.S. Eliot, a prominent modernist poet and critic, is known for his penetrating insights into literature. His analysis of *Hamlet* challenges traditional interpretations that label Hamlet as simply mad or melancholic. Instead, Eliot posits that Hamlet's true malady is a reflection of the complexities and contradictions inherent in the human condition. He argues that Hamlet's struggle is not merely personal but universal, embodying the existential anxieties and moral ambiguities that define humanity. In his essay, "Hamlet and His Problems," Eliot presents a diagnosis of Hamlet's "malady" not as madness or melancholia, but as a profound exploration of the human condition. The books by Stoll and Robertson were themselves a reaction against the Romantic- psychological criticism led by S. T. Coleridge in the nineteenth century and by A. C. Bradley at the beginning of the twentieth. This brand of criticism sought to explain Hamlet's delay in terms of some sort of spiritual or intellectual malady leading to his propensity to excessive thought and over-delicate sensibilities. Both Stoll and Robertson argued that as Shakespeare's play was derived from earlier plays on Hamlet Shakespeare took some material from those plays but could not somehow fully integrate it. For example, the problem of delay in the earlier plays was due to physical difficulties. Similarly, madness in them was obviously feigned to avoid suspicion.

Eliot endorses the view that the text of the play is a palimpsest. He says that in the three possible pieces of evidence-Kyd's *The Spanish Tragedy*, the tale given in *Belle-forest*, and a version of the play acted in Germany-it is obvious that Hamlet's delay is due to purely practical difficulties in killing a

king who is always surrounded by Swiss bodyguards. But Shakespeare turned the focus from revenge to Hamlet's over-consciousness of his mother's guilt. This is how Eliot comments on Robertson's reading of the text: "The upshot of Mr. Robertson's examination is, we believe, irrefragable: that Shakespeare's Hamlet, so far as it is Shakespeare's, is a play dealing with the effect of a mother's guilt upon her son, and that Shakespeare was unable to impose this motive successfully upon the 'intractable' material of the old play" (Sacred Wood, 98). Eliot not only accepts Robertson's theory of a "text in evolution" but goes further and says that even Shakespeare's contribution to the multi-layered text is not all of a piece: "Hamlet, like the sonnets, is full of some stuff that the writer could not drag to light, contemplate, or manipulate into art." And from this he arrives at his most controversial thesis: "So far from being Shakespeare's masterpiece, the play [Hamlet] is most certainly an artistic failure" (98). Eliot's critical perspective shifts the focus from Hamlet's actions to his existential dilemma, providing a framework for understanding the character's psychological depth and its reflection on human nature.

The reason for this failure, according to T. S. Eliot lies in Shakespeare's failure to provide a suitable "objective correlative" for Hamlet's emotion which seems to be in excess of the given facts. Eliot then defines objective correlative as a "set of objects, a situation, a chain of events which shall be the formula of that particular emotion; such that when the external facts, which must terminate in sensory experience, are given, the emotion is immediately evoked" (100). In other words, an objective correlative is the external, theatrical and objective equivalent of the internal emotion of a character or the one expressed in the play. One of Eliot's significant contributions to literary criticism is the concept of the "objective correlative," which he defines as a set of objects, situations, or events that evoke a particular emotion. In *Hamlet*, Eliot finds that the play lacks a suitable objective correlative to justify Hamlet's intense emotions and actions. This lack, Eliot argues, contributes to the play's failure to provide a coherent explanation for Hamlet's behavior, thereby highlighting the broader human struggle to find meaning in a chaotic world (Eliot, 1920). In Hamlet, says Eliot, Hamlet's disgust is caused and aroused by his mother, but being an insipid and insignificant character she cannot be the objective equivalent for his emotion. Eliot then seeks to root the supposed lack of the objective correlative in the writer's own inability to understand and grasp the material he was tackling:

Dr. Eliot's diagnosis of Hamlet's "malady" typically refers to an analysis by a literary critic or a fictional portrayal of a psychiatrist diagnosing Hamlet's condition in William Shakespeare's play. While specific details about Dr. Eliot's exact diagnosis might vary depending on the source, Hamlet is often analyzed through various psychological lenses, including:

1. Melancholy and Depression: Hamlet displays classic symptoms of depression, including profound sadness, lack of motivation, and contemplation of suicide.
2. Oedipal Complex: Sigmund Freud's psychoanalytic theory suggests Hamlet has repressed desires for his mother, contributing to his internal conflict. Hamlet's psychological complexity is central to Eliot's analysis. Unlike other Shakespearean characters whose motivations are clear, Hamlet remains enigmatic. His actions and inactions stem from a profound internal conflict, which Eliot interprets as a reflection of the modern human psyche grappling with existential questions.
3. Existential Crisis: Hamlet's soliloquies, especially "To be or not to be," reflect his existential dread and philosophical pondering over life, death, and the meaning of existence.
4. Grief and Trauma: Hamlet's behavior is heavily influenced by the grief over his father's death and the trauma of his mother's quick remarriage.
5. Existential Readings: Existential readings of *Hamlet* also owe much to Eliot's critique. By highlighting the play's exploration of existential themes, Eliot paved the way for interpretations that see Hamlet as a precursor to modern existentialist thought. Critics like Jean-Paul Sartre and Albert Camus have drawn parallels between Hamlet's dilemmas and the existentialist themes of absurdity, freedom, and the search for meaning.

Dr. Eliot might explore these or other psychological aspects to diagnose Hamlet's behavior and mental state. If you have a specific text or reference to Dr. Eliot's diagnosis, providing that context would allow for a more accurate and detailed explanation.

Hamlet was written around 1600 or early 1601, a time when Shakespeare was deeply interested in exploring the relationship between the mind and the world it interacts with. This period in Shakespeare's career is marked by a fascination with how people perceive the world and how those perceptions can be distorted. His plays from this time often grapple with how knowledge relates to the individual, and how one's imagination can be either true or distorted.

Hamlet, one of Shakespeare's most renowned tragedies, dives into complex themes such as revenge, madness, mortality, and existential dread. It portrays a narrative filled with murder, suicide, and madness, offering both melodrama and a nuanced analysis of character. As one of Shakespeare's earliest great tragedies, **Hamlet** stands out for its deep self-awareness. Set against a Renaissance backdrop of art, learning, and intrigue, the play features its central character, Hamlet, as a Renaissance scholar-prince who is clever, melancholic, and introspective.

Hamlet, much like a real person, resists full interpretation. Shakespeare uses him to explore the complexities of action and the reflective mind. The play features captivating language and varied moods, from witty exchanges with Polonius and the actors to profound soliloquies about drunkenness and mental imbalance. Shakespeare's dramatic, intellectual, and expressive abilities are at their peak during this time. His works from this period, including **Hamlet**, reflect a shift towards a darker exploration of human experience. The plays delve into destructive passions that challenge the moral order and bring ruin to both the innocent and the guilty. Even in his comedies, the tone often leans towards the grave or fierce, focusing on the flaws and sins of humanity.

A critical analysis of "Hamlet" can focus on several key aspects:

1. Themes

Revenge and Justice: The central theme of the play revolves around Hamlet's quest for revenge against his uncle, King Claudius, who murdered Hamlet's father. The ethical and moral implications of revenge are explored deeply, raising questions about justice and the consequences of vengeance.

Madness

Traditional interpretations often view Hamlet as either genuinely mad or feigning madness to achieve his ends. However, Eliot suggests that this binary perspective oversimplifies Hamlet's condition. Instead, Hamlet's behavior can be seen as a manifestation of the broader human experience of disorientation and confusion in the face of existential uncertainty. Hamlet's soliloquies, particularly "To be, or not to be," reveal his deep contemplation of life's meaning and the nature of existence, which transcend simple madness or sanity (Shakespeare, 1603). Madness, both real and feigned, is a pivotal theme. Hamlet's sanity is a topic of continuous debate. He adopts an "antic disposition" to uncover the truth about his father's death, but the line between his act and genuine madness blurs as the play progresses. Ophelia's descent into madness and subsequent death adds another layer, contrasting her genuine madness with Hamlet's ambiguous state.

Mortality and the Fear of Death

Hamlet is preoccupied with death, not only because of his father's murder but also as a fundamental aspect of the human condition. Death pervades the play, from the ghost of King Hamlet to the numerous deaths by the end. The famous "To be or not to be" soliloquy explores existential questions about life, death, and what comes after, reflecting Hamlet's deep philosophical and existential struggles. The graveyard scene, where Hamlet reflects on the skull of Yorick, epitomizes this preoccupation. Hamlet's musings on the inevitability of death and the futility of life's pursuits highlight the universal human fear of mortality and the unknown.

The Weight of Conscience

Eliot emphasizes the role of conscience in Hamlet's actions. Hamlet's acute awareness of moral and ethical dilemmas paralyzes him, reflecting the human struggle to reconcile inner values with external actions. This paralysis is evident in Hamlet's hesitation to avenge his father's murder. His introspective nature and constant questioning of the righteousness of his cause echo the modern individual's search for moral clarity in an ambiguous world.

The Human Condition in *Hamlet*

Eliot's diagnosis of Hamlet's malady as human centers on the play's exploration of universal themes such as mortality, identity, and the search for meaning. Hamlet's journey mirrors the human quest to understand and cope with these existential concerns.

Identity and Self-Discovery

Hamlet's struggle with identity is another facet of his malady. Throughout the play, he grapples with his role as a son, prince, and avenger. His feigned madness can be seen as a way to explore and express his true self, free from the constraints of societal expectations. This quest for self-discovery is a central theme in the human experience, as individuals seek to define themselves in relation to the world around them.

The Search for Meaning

At its core, *Hamlet* is a meditation on the search for meaning in a seemingly indifferent universe. Hamlet's existential crises and his philosophical reflections resonate with the modern human condition, characterized by a sense of dislocation and a yearning for purpose. Eliot's analysis underscores this aspect, portraying Hamlet as a figure who embodies the struggle to find meaning in life amidst chaos and uncertainty.

2. Characters

Hamlet

Hamlet is a complex character, embodying a deep intellectualism and philosophical inquiry. His indecision and contemplation are central to the play's narrative. His struggle with taking action, his reflections on life and death, and his moral integrity make him one of Shakespeare's most intricate characters.

Claudius

As the antagonist, Claudius is a character driven by ambition and power. His guilt and internal conflict are revealed in his soliloquy when he attempts to pray. Despite his remorse, he continues to commit further immoral acts to maintain his power.

Gertrude

Gertrude, Hamlet's mother, is often seen as a passive character, whose hasty marriage to Claudius raises questions about her loyalty and morality. Her relationship with Hamlet is complex, embodying both affection and misunderstanding.

Ophelia

Ophelia represents innocence and obedience but is also a tragic figure. Her descent into madness and death highlight the impact of political and familial machinations on the individual, especially women.

3. Symbolism and Imagery-

Shakespeare employs rich symbolism and imagery throughout the play. The appearance of the ghost, the recurring motif of decay and corruption (e.g., "Something is rotten in the state of Denmark"), and the use of theatrical metaphors (such as the play-within-a-play) all serve to deepen the thematic content and emotional impact of the narrative.

4. Literary Devices

Soliloquies

Hamlet's soliloquies are crucial for understanding his inner thoughts and conflicts. They provide direct insight into his psyche and are essential for the development of his character.

Wordplay and Puns

Shakespeare's use of language, including wordplay and puns, adds layers of meaning and often reflects the complexity of the characters' thoughts and feelings. Hamlet, in particular, uses wordplay to convey his wit and intelligence.

5. Philosophical and Psychological Interpretations

Modern psychological approaches to *Hamlet* often draw on Eliot's analysis to explore the character's inner turmoil. Psychoanalytic critics, for instance, examine Hamlet's Oedipal complex, his unconscious desires, and his struggles with identity and agency. These interpretations build on Eliot's view of Hamlet as a deeply conflicted individual whose malady is rooted in the complexities of the human psyche.

Existentialism

Hamlet's soliloquies reflect existential themes, questioning the nature of existence and the purpose of life. His famous lines contemplate the hardships of life versus the fear of the unknown in death.

Psychoanalysis

Freudian interpretations often explore Hamlet's Oedipal complex, suggesting that his hesitation to kill Claudius is linked to repressed desires for his mother, Gertrude.

6. Modern and Moral Interpretations of Hamlet

Ethical and Moral Interpretations

Eliot's emphasis on conscience and moral ambiguity in *Hamlet* has also influenced ethical and moral interpretations of the play. Critics examine how Hamlet's ethical dilemmas reflect broader questions about justice, revenge, and the human condition. These interpretations resonate with Eliot's view of Hamlet as a figure grappling with the complexities of moral decision-making in an uncertain world.

Eliot's Influence on Modern Interpretations of Hamlet

Eliot's critique of *Hamlet* has had a profound impact on subsequent literary interpretations. By framing Hamlet's malady as a reflection of the human condition, Eliot opened new avenues for understanding the play's psychological and existential dimensions. His insights have influenced modern readings of Hamlet, emphasizing the character's depth and the play's relevance to contemporary issues.

"Hamlet" remains a profound exploration of human nature and the complexities of life and death. Its enduring relevance is due to Shakespeare's deep understanding of the human condition, masterful character development, and intricate use of language and themes. Whether viewed through a psychological, existential, or purely literary lens, "Hamlet" continues to offer rich material for critical analysis and interpretation.

Hamlet (the man) is dominated by an emotion which is inexpressible, because it is in excess of the facts as they appear. And the supposed identity of Hamlet with his author is genuine to this point: that Hamlet's bafflement at the absence of objective equivalent to his feelings is a prolongation of the bafflement of his creator in the face of his artistic problem" (101).

There cannot be much quarrel about Eliot's theory of the objective correlative. Nor can anybody contradict the idea that art expresses emotion.. What is wrong with Eliot's argument vis- a-vis Hamlet is his inability to understand what Shakespeare has tried to make so explicit in the play. To be specific, it is true that Gertrude, as she appears in the play, is a sketchy, insipid and insignificant charam peanut Hamlet's emotion is aroused not by what she is but by what she has done and by the fact that she is his mother, whom het sad always thought of as a model of womanhood. As though he anticipated Eliot's attack on his play on this is ground, Shakespeare shows the confrontation between

The mother and the son in the "Closet Scene" (III.5). When Hamlet speaks "daggers" to her, she asks him,

What have I done that thou dar'st wag thy tongue
In noise so rude against me? (III. 5. 39-40),
At this, Hamlet bursts out furiously,
Such an act
That blurs the grace and blush of ,
Calls virtue hypocrite, takes off the rose
From the fair forehead of an innocent love And sets a blister there, makes marriage vows
As false as dicers' oaths... (40-45)

Thus, even if we accept the theory of the objective correlative in its totality, Gertrude's over-hasty and incestuous marriage with the beast-like Claudius is the cause of Hamlet's disgust with her. What hurts him most is that she is his mother ("Were it not so..," he says at one point) and he cannot alter this fact. Moreover, he had always considered her a model of feminine modesty and virtue. If she could fall, which woman would not? This is why he says that her action has put a "blister" mark (the sign put on the forehead of a prostitute in Shakespeare's time) on the forehead of any innocent girl. So it is wrong to say that Gertrude is not a suitable objective correlative for Hamlet's emotion.

My interpretation does not of course explain the entire mystery surrounding Hamlet's reactions and speeches. But I hope that it succeeds in questioning Eliot's application of his theory of objective correlative to Hamlet. As for the mystery itself, even A. C. Bradley, that great champion of the "character is destiny theory," had to concede that "tragedy would not be tragedy if it were not a painful mystery" (Shakespearean Tragedy, 7). Hamlet is indeed a highly self-reflexive text engaged in a ceaseless free play of signifiers in search of a "decentred" central signified. And in this lies its real beauty and fascination.

Conclusion

T.S. Eliot's diagnosis of Hamlet's malady as human offers a profound reinterpretation of Shakespeare's character and the play as a whole. By shifting the focus from Hamlet's supposed madness to his existential struggles, Eliot illuminates the play's exploration of the human condition. Hamlet's journey, marked by introspection, moral ambiguity, and a search for meaning, resonates with the modern human experience. Eliot's insights have significantly influenced subsequent interpretations of *Hamlet*, emphasizing the character's psychological depth and the play's enduring relevance to contemporary existential concerns.

References

- Shakespeare, W. (1603). *Hamlet*. London: Oxford University Press
- Eliot, T. S. (1920). *The Sacred Wood: Essays on Poetry and Criticism*. Methuen.
- Bradley, A. C. Shakespearean Tragedy (1904): Macmillan, 1977. Eliot, T. S. The Sacred Wood (1920) London: Methuen, 1967.

*** **